

A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO "HUL LTD"

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Abstract:

Customer satisfaction is the important thing in the marketing concept. The companies cannot sustain forever in the market without satisfying customers. Consumers minds changes very rapidly so it is very important to keep them loyal. Whatever the customer wants to get from a product that should be always provided by the companies and keep customers satisfied, if this thing does not happen then consumer will stop buying. Customer satisfaction is a term frequently used in marketing. It is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpasses customer's expectations. This paper titled "A Descriptive Study on Customer Satisfaction With Special Reference to HUL Ltd" aims to understand about the Customer satisfaction of indulekha products in today's dynamic business environment. Indulekha is the one of the leading brand of cosmetics products. According to this study, the most of the customers are focused mainly on the quality of the product other than cost consideration and also they are expecting more advanced products from indulekha as a brand. Now day's customers are much afraid of skin, hair, and their beauty, and also they fear skin color and hair loss. These factors play an important role in sales of cosmetics products in India. So the company has to ensure the customers satisfaction for survival in the market. In the business arena more and more organizations are able to realize the importance of having good relations with their clients. Customers are most valuable to any brands success. Good relationship with the customer is an important aspect when it comes brand development. There is a probability that satisfied customer will continue to purchase from the same company and become brand loyal. There might be a situation when customer becomes very negative and terminates to the use of a product due several problems in it. This will slowly tamper the brand value and companies' performance will be severely affected. This study indicates that Customer satisfaction is vital for any brand to become market leader in today's competitive world.

Index Terms: Customer Satisfaction, Brand, Marketing & HLL Products

1. Introduction:

Customer one of important element in any business organization. The marketer in modern era believes that customer is the back bone of any company. One who consumes a product or service is called customer. According to modern concept of marketing, customers have great importance. The aim of marketing is to meet and satisfy customers' needs and wants because of the changing mind of the customers. Modern customers view the product from the different angles. The post and pre-purchase valuation, the knowledge from the other customers, the knowledge from the other Medias, evaluation of the other substitute products etc, play a vital role in consumer's decision making process. Customers would desire to get the product at an easily acceptable place with maximum outlet. Thus the marketers must study their target customer's wants, perceptions, preferences and buying behavior. Such study will provide clues for developing new products, product features, price channels, and other marketing mix elements. Consumerism and the services offered to customers are important. High consumerism is due to some legislation like consumer protection Act

1998 and others. High literacy and media plays tremendous important role in consumerism. Buyer behavior is an important factor in marketing. The variations in their behavior are due to some factors of buyer's behavior. If the consumer is not satisfied for anyone of the reasons he will switch to other brands. Customer satisfaction is a term frequently used in marketing. It is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpass customer expectation. Customer satisfaction is defined as "the number of customers, or percentage of total customers, whose reported experience with a firm, its products, or its services (ratings) exceeds specified satisfaction goals."

It is seen as a key performance indicator within business and is often part of a Balanced Scorecard. In a competitive marketplace where businesses compete for customers, customer satisfaction is seen as a key differentiator and increasingly has become a key element of business strategy. Within organizations, customer satisfaction ratings can have powerful effects. They focus employees on the importance of fulfilling customers' expectations. Furthermore, when these ratings dip, they warn of problems that can affect sales and profitability. These metrics quantify an important dynamic. When a brand has loyal customers, it gains positive word-of-mouth marketing, which is both free and highly effective. Therefore, it is essential for businesses to effectively manage customer satisfaction. To be able do this, firms need reliable measures of satisfaction. In researching satisfaction, firms generally ask customers whether their product or service has met or exceeded expectations. Thus, expectations are a key factor behind satisfaction. When customers have high expectations and the reality falls short, they will be disappointed and will likely rate their experience as less than satisfying. For this reason, a luxury resort, for example, might receive a lower satisfaction rating than a budget motel - even though its facilities and service would be deemed superior in absolute terms.

The importance of customer satisfaction diminishes when a firm has increased bargaining power. For example, cell phone plan providers, participate in an industry that is an oligopoly, where only a few suppliers of a certain product or service exist. As such, many cell phone plan contracts have a lot of fine print with provisions that they would never get away if there were, say, a hundred cell phone plan providers, because customer satisfaction would be way too low, and customers would easily have the option of leaving for a better contract offer.

Customer satisfaction provides a leading indicator of consumer purchase intentions and loyalty. Customer satisfaction data are among the most frequently collected indicators of market perceptions. Organizations need to retain existing customers while targeting non-customers. Measuring customer satisfaction provides an indication of how successful the organization is at providing products and/or services to the marketplace. Customer satisfaction is an ambiguous and abstract concept and the actual manifestation of the state of satisfaction will vary from person to person and product/service to product/service. The state of satisfaction depends on a number of both psychological and physical variables which correlate with satisfaction behaviors such as return and recommend rate. The level of satisfaction can also vary depending on other options the customer may have and other products against which the customer can compare the organization's products.

Consumers worldwide are going green and this is especially true in the cosmetics market. Over the last few years, growth in the market for cosmetics has been driven by products that use natural or herbal components.. There has been a shift in universal trend from synthetic to herbal medicine recently. It is ancient wisdom that plants have

therapeutic value and are used to treat various diseases since Neanderthal age. All ancient civilizations in the world are known to use plants for medicinal purposes. Ayurveda and traditional Chinese medicines are well known to the world for their natural ingredients and multiple benefits. Companies are increasingly feeling pressurized to focus on sustainability and reduce their environmental footprints. They are becoming conscious of the ingredients that go into the products that they use and are averse to chemicals that are known to cause side effects. On the supply side, companies are engaging in advanced research of plant-derived peptides, encapsulated actives, active plant stem cells, complex extraction processes, and clinical testing to deliver products that are acceptable to the well-informed customers.

Indians have been traditionally inclined toward natural products for their beauty needs. India has a history and knowledge of using natural products. While consumers in the rest of the world have to be educated about the benefits of natural herbs, this knowledge is well inherited in India from generations. The need is for companies to translate the ancient ayurvedic recipes into modern easy to use formats with superior quality. During the last decade, the herbal beauty care business has emerged as the new growth frontier for beauty business in India. The emphasis has been on the spectacular growth of the herbal and ayurvedic beauty products business. Today, the Indian cosmetics industry has a plethora of herbal cosmetic brands like Forest Essentials, Biotique, Himalaya, Blossom Kochhar, VLCC, Dabur and Lotus; and many more are adding to the list. In addition to a widening base of consumers, color cosmetics and anti-aging and anti-wrinkle creams are expected to be the future drivers of growth in this segment. The market for ayurvedic cosmetics products in India is expected to grow at a rapid pace over the coming decades. The market is only beginning to get populated with ayurvedic brands and it will be a while until it gets too crowded. Brands like Patanjali is also catching up the markets and making it more competitive. Ayurvedic manufacturers are investing in research and constantly coming up with new and innovative technology and products that are resulting in better and more effective ayurvedic cosmetics.

Mosons Extraction is one of the leading Ayurvedic pharmaceutical industries. It has great presence in southern part of India and specially in state of Kerala. It has become one of the leading players in the cosmetic sector. Mosons extraction mainly deals with the manufacturing of beauty care products, cosmetics, which include oil, creams face pack etc. The main products of the company are indulekha hair care oil, indulekha skin care oil, indulekha coconut milk shampoo, indulekha white soap. Below are the list of the products available under Brand Indulekha.

- ✓ Indulekha Bringa Hair Care Oil
- ✓ Indulekha Skin Care Oil
- ✓ Indulekha Satapatri Face Cream
- ✓ Indulekha Akrot Face Pack
- ✓ Indulekha Coconut Milk Shampoo
- ✓ Indulekha White Soap
- ✓ Indulekha Jasmine & Sandal Soap
- ✓ Vayodha Hair Care Oil
- ✓ Fist Touch Baby Care Oil

This paper will discuss the importance of customer satisfaction towards herbal products and in recent time how multinationals have recognize the importance of ayurvedic products specially in segment of hair oil. Indulekha Bringha or simply Indulekha Hair Oil is complete ayurvedic hair care oil to all modern day hair problems. In Ayurveda hair care involves two stages: Kesapadasamanam (Hair fall reduction),

Kesavardhanam (Stimulate new hair growth). There are specific herbs and natural elements that are prescribed in Ayurveda to prevent hair fall and promote new hair growth. Indulekha Bringha hair oil is constituted by these specific herbs and natural elements, thus bringing to you an Authentic Ayurvedic solution for total hair care. The 100% natural herbs are prepared in a base of pure virgin coconut oil, thus not only providing hair treatment but also nutritionally enriching your hair. Since it is completely based on natural herbs and extracts, Indulekha Bringha hair oil is side-effect free and suitable for everybody.

2. Scope of Objective of the Study:

Customer satisfaction research help the organization to better plan their business, marketing and sales activities, safeguard and increase its revenue streams, safeguard and increase its customer base, optimize costs of sales, increase brand value, adjust competitive strategies, safeguard company from competitive actions, speed new product adoption. This study also helps to know the customer satisfaction of Indulekha products in Kasarkode market. This study assists to identify the opinion of the customers of Indulekha products. To assess the customer awareness about Indulekha brand.

3. Research Methodology:

For the purposes of the study data collected are analyzed and arrived on some conclusions. The research is conducted with the help of well formed questionnaire to make this study in a better way and collected data from each sides of the Kasarkode district and over 100 respondents are interviewed from the different parts of the District. The actual information collected is arranged systematically and represented all of them in graphs. The main aim of graphical representation of data was to give a clear cut idea about the statements of problems. The convenience method of sampling is used and hypothesis testing is used for the research.

Data Interpretation and Analysis:

Table 1: Age Wise Distribution of the Respondents

Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Below 20	37	37
20-40	40	40
40-60	21	21
Above 60	2	2
Total	100	100

Interpretation: Above table shows the age wise the distribution of the respondents. Out of 100 respondents, 37 percent of the respondents are below 20 years and 40 percent of the respondents are in the age group of 20-40, 21 percent of the respondents are in the group of 40-60

Table 2: Gender Wise Distribution of Respondents

Sex	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	39	39
Female	61	61
Total	100	100

Interpretation: Above tables shows the sex wise distribution of the respondents. Out of 100 respondents, 39 percentages of the respondents are male and 61 percentages of the respondents are female

4. Conclusion:

Customer satisfaction is the important thing in the marketing concept. Because without satisfying customers a company which cannot sustain in the market forever , not only that customers mind is a changing one. Whatever the customer wants to get from a product that much should be provided by the companies to satisfy customers otherwise customers will stop the buying. In the business arena more and more organizations are able to realize the importance of having good relations with their clients. In this manner many industries are trying to identify ways on how to promote or enhance client relationships. The customer company-relationship is based on a continuum where in both always a share and lost for good relationship occupy the two extremes of the continuum. In an always a share relationship transactions are arms length and discreet. Customers are valuable and at the same time replaceable. On the other hand in a lost for good relationship the probability that the customer will purchase again from the same company is extremely low when the customer decides to terminate the use of a product due to product problems. With these problems the performance of the business are being affected negatively. In order to solve the issue different methods can be used to ensure good client relations. Hence this part of the study will provide literatures focusing on the ways on how to improve client relation. In this study it is examine that most of the customers are satisfied with the brand indulekha and overall satisfaction level is quite high compared to other Brands. Major part of customers expecting more advanced products from indulekha brand and are

brand conscious. Over all the peoples are opined that quality of Indulekha products is good. All the customers are focused mainly on the quality of the product other than cost consideration. The factors influencing purchase decisions are from the advice of friends and relatives mostly.

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